

THERE ARE NO SOCIALIST PRIMES LESS THAN 10^9

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Abstract

There are no primes p with $5 < p < 10^9$ for which $2!, 3!, \dots, (p-1)!$ are all distinct modulo p . It is conjectured that there are no such primes.

1. The Problem

Erdős asked whether there are any primes $p > 5$ for which the numbers $2!, 3!, \dots, (p-1)!$ are all distinct modulo p . Were these $p-2$ factorials all distinct then the $p-1$ non-zero residue classes modulo p would contain at most one of them. Motivated by this redistribution of resources amongst classes we shall call such a prime p a *socialist prime*. Rokowska and Schinzel [7]² proved the following.

Theorem 1 (Rokowska and Schinzel). *A prime p is a socialist prime only if $p \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$, and*

$$\left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = -1, \quad \left(\frac{-23}{p}\right) = 1. \quad (1)$$

Moreover, if a socialist prime exists then none of the numbers $2!, 3!, \dots, (p-1)!$ is congruent to $-((p-1)/2)!$.

The proof given by Rokowska and Schinzel is fairly straightforward. One may dismiss primes of the form $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, since such primes have the property [5, Theorem 114] that $((p-1)/2)! \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{p}$. By Wilson's theorem, $(p-1)! \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$ and $(p-2)! \equiv (p-1)!(p-1)^{-1} \equiv +1 \pmod{p}$, conditions which, when taken together, prohibit p from being a socialist prime. Henceforth consider $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, in which case

$$\left\{ \left(\frac{p-1}{2}\right)! \right\}^2 \equiv -1 \pmod{p}. \quad (2)$$

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²This problem also appears as **F11** in Richard Guy's insuperable book [4].

If $2!, 3!, \dots, (p-1)!$ are all distinct modulo p then they must be permutations of the numbers $1, 2, \dots, p-1$ with the exception of some r , with $1 \leq r \leq p-1$, whence

$$\prod_{n=2}^{p-1} n! \equiv \frac{(p-1)!}{r} \pmod{p},$$

so that

$$1 \equiv r \prod_{n=1}^{p-2} n! \equiv r((p-1)/2)! \prod_{1 \leq k < \frac{p-1}{2}} k!(p-k-1)! \pmod{p}.$$

Applying (2) and Wilson's theorem gives

$$r \prod_{1 \leq k < \frac{p-1}{2}} (-1)^{k+1} \equiv -\left(\frac{p-1}{2}\right)! \pmod{p},$$

so that $r \equiv \pm((p-1)/2)! \pmod{p}$. One may dismiss the positive root, since r is not congruent to any $j!$ for $1 \leq j \leq p-1$. Hence

$$\prod_{1 \leq k < \frac{p-1}{2}} (-1)^{k+1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}.$$

Equating powers of (-1) gives

$$\sum_{1 \leq k < \frac{p-1}{2}} (k+1) = \frac{(p-3)(p+3)}{8} \equiv 0 \pmod{2},$$

whence, since $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, one may conclude that $p \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$.

The conditions in (1) are a little more subtle. Consider a polynomial $F(x) = x^n + a_1x^{n-1} + \dots + a_0$ with integral coefficients and discriminant D . A theorem by Stickelberger (see, e.g. [2, p. 249]) gives $\left(\frac{D}{p}\right) = (-1)^{n-\nu}$, where ν is the number of factors of $F(x)$ that are irreducible modulo p . Consider the two congruences

$$x(x+1) - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}, \quad x(x+1)(x+2) - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p},$$

the polynomials in which have discriminants 5 and -23 . For the former, if $\left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = 1$, then, by Stickelberger's theorem, there are two irreducible factors, whence the congruence factors and has a solution. Therefore $(x+1)! \equiv (x-1)! \pmod{p}$ and p is not a socialist prime. Likewise for the latter: if $\left(\frac{-23}{p}\right) = -1$ then there are two irreducible factors, whence $(x+2)! \equiv (x-1)! \pmod{p}$. This completes the proof of Theorem 1.

One cannot continue down this path directly. Consider $x(x+1)(x+2)(x+3) - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ which has a solution if and only if $y(y+2) - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ has a solution,

where $y = x(x + 3)$. Hence $(y + 1)^2 \equiv 2 \pmod{p}$, which implies 2 is a quadratic residue modulo p — a contradiction since $p \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$.

Instead one can consider the congruence

$$x(x + 1)(x + 2)(x + 3)(x + 4)(x + 5) - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p},$$

which is soluble precisely when $y(y + 4)(y + 6) - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ is soluble, where $y = x(x + 5)$. The cubic congruence in y has discriminant 1957, whence, by Stickelberger's theorem, if $\left(\frac{1957}{p}\right) = -1$ then $y(y + 4)(y + 6)$ has a linear factor. To deduce that $(x + 5)! \equiv (x - 1)! \pmod{p}$ we need to know that $y \equiv x(x + 5) \pmod{p}$ is soluble, that is, we need to know that $4y + 25$ is a quadratic residue modulo p . We can therefore add a condition to (1), namely

Theorem 2. *A necessary condition that p be a socialist prime is*

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{1957}{p}\right) &= 1, \quad \text{or} \\ \left(\frac{1957}{p}\right) &= -1 \quad \& \quad \left(\frac{4y + 25}{p}\right) = -1, \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

for all y satisfying $y(y + 4)(y + 6) - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$.

2. Computation and Conclusion

Rokowska and Schinzel showed that the only primes $5 < p < 1000$ satisfying $p \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$ and (1) were

$$13, 173, 197, 277, 317, 397, 653, 853, 877, 997.$$

Using Jacobi's *Canon arithmeticus* they showed that for each prime there existed $1 < k < j \leq p - 1$ for which $k! \equiv j! \pmod{p}$.

I am grateful to David Harvey who extended this to show that there are no socialist primes less than 10^6 . This computation took 45 minutes on a 1.7 GHz Intel Core i7 machine. Tomás Oliveira e Silva extended this to $p < 10^9$, a calculation which took 3 days.

The following example shows the utility of adding the condition (3). Using the conditions $p \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$ and (1), it is easy to check that there are at most 4908 socialist primes up to 10^6 . These need to be checked to see whether there are values of k and j for which $k! \equiv j! \pmod{p}$. Including the condition (3) means that there are at most 3662 socialist primes up to 10^6 that need to be checked.

To extend the range of computation beyond 10^9 it would be desirable to add another condition arising from a suitable congruence. The congruence leading to (3) was of degree 6; no other suitable congruence was found for degrees 8 and 9.

In [1] the authors considered $F(p)$ defined to be the number of distinct residue classes modulo p that are not contained in the sequence $1!, 2!, 3!, \dots$. They showed that $\limsup_{p \rightarrow \infty} F(p) = \infty$; for the problem involving socialist primes one wishes to show that $F(p) = 2$ never occurs. It would therefore be of interest to study small values of $F(p)$. This problem has also been considered and recast in [3] and [6].

Finally, one may examine the problem naïvely as follows. Ignore the conditions $p \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$ and (1) — including these only reduces the likelihood of there being socialist primes. For $2 \leq k \neq j \leq p-2$ we want $p \nmid j! - k!$. There are $\binom{p-3}{2} = (p-3)(p-4)/2$ admissible values of (k, j) . Assuming, speciously, that the probability that p does not divide N ‘random’ integers is $(1 - 1/p)^N$ one concludes that the probability of finding a socialist prime is

$$\left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right)^{\frac{(p-3)(p-4)}{2}} \rightarrow e^{-\frac{(7-p)}{2}},$$

for large p .

Given this estimate, and the computational data, it seems reasonable to conjecture that there are no socialist primes.

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